

Analysis of Service Quality Improvement Using Service Quality (SERVQUAL) and Importance Performance Analysis (IPA) Methods (Case Study at PDAM Banggai Regency)

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ABSTRACT: PDAM Kab. Banggai is a service company that has the aim of meeting the needs in the field of clean water must provide the best service. The purpose of this research is to analyze service quality based on customer satisfaction and find out the factors that affect service quality to get a solution to the causes of problems based on service quality. This research will use the servqual method to measure service quality with the level of perceptions and expectations of consumers in the services provided by service providers. Furthermore, the *Importance Performance Analysis* (IPA) method is used in measuring the level of importance and performance so that the company can find out the attributes that need to be improved and maintained in service based on a Cartesian diagram and will produce a basis for customer satisfaction. After that, the Fishbone Diagram is used to analyze the consequences by finding and describing the factors that cause the existing problems. Then given the proposed improvements and submitted PDAM to be followed up by PDAM Kab. Banggai. The results of the Service Quality analysis of the quality of service of PDAM Kab. Banggai obtained a negative Gap in the Reliability dimension at attribute B5 (-1.200), in the Responsiveness dimension obtained a negative Gap at attribute C1 (-1.140), at attribute C2 with a negative Gap (-1.120) and in the Assurance dimension with a negative Gap (-0.560). The results of the analysis using Importance Performance Analysis obtained 4 attributes that are among the top priorities for improvement, namely the attributes contained in quadrant I. The four attributes that are the top priorities for improvement are the ease with which customers can submit complaints online to the PDAM, employees are responsive when answering complaints from customers through online media such as whatsapp, officers contact customers when they cannot fulfill the specified repair promise and the use of PDAM services Kab. Banggai is guaranteed to be safe when making payment transactions. The proposed improvements given to PDAM Kab. Banggai are Attribute D2, namely conducting a re-check before making payment bills to customers, collaborating with third parties such as banks and outlets (indomaret, alfamidi, etc.) and making payment applications directly linked to PDAM accounts so that there is no manipulation during the payment process. Attribute C2 is instilling a sense of responsibility in officers and openness to customers to contact customers as soon as possible if something happens or cannot fulfill the specified repair promise, the need to make SOPs so that they have standard provisions for contacting customers if they cannot fulfill repair promises and provide facilities to contact customers. Attribute C1, namely recruiting Customer Service and implementing a 24-hour work shift system to be available if there are complaints via messages or calls, implementing online complaint services for 24 hours to be responsive to answering customer complaints and providing social media accounts that are always updated to provide information about PDAM and responsive when there are complaints from customers online. Attribute B5, namely implementing a work shift system for officers who are available when there are complaints via messages or calls, implementing online complaint services through social media and providing media for customers to submit complaints online such as providing PDAM contact numbers that are always active 24 hours. For further research, it is hoped that it will be able to research to implement the proposed improvements provided and analyze the quality of service after implementing the proposed improvements provided by the author so that the effectiveness of the services that have been implemented can be known.

KEYWORDS: PDAM Kab. Banggai, customer satisfaction, service quality, Service Quality (SERVQUAL), Importance Performance Analysis (IPA), Fishbone Diagram

1. INTRODUCTION

Water is one of the most important health elements for all life on earth. In modern life, water has a major role as a measure of environmental balance, and people need water everywhere, such as in agriculture, business, households, health to industrial processing needs so that the function of water is not only limited to carrying out economic functions but also social functions. The social and economic functions that water has in order to fulfill daily needs are important things that must be considered because along with the increasing population, the need for water will inevitably increase (Syah, 2019).

The need for clean water is essential for survival. Therefore, the central government through local governments formed an agency called PDAM with the aim of exploring regional resources, especially drinking water, which can contribute to the region. As a service company, PDAM is not only able to generate revenue, but also provide the best service to customers (Priyanka et al.,

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2022).

One of the service companies in the Central Sulawesi region that provides the benefits of water resources is PDAM Banggai Regency. As one of the public services that has the aim of meeting the needs in the field of clean water, it is obliged to provide the best service. Public services provided by the government are assessed by the quality of service to the user community. The government provides services so that users can enjoy the services provided. The number of complaints that have arisen from the community about PDAM Banggai Regency services is to see how the level of service provided to the community on service quality and customer satisfaction. It aims to create a good image in the eyes of the community because if there is no improvement in terms of service quality, customer satisfaction will continue to decline and the number of consumer complaints about PDAM performance in terms of service quality will be higher (Bakhtiar, 2010). The Regional Drinking Water Company (PDAM) was formed with the aim of meeting the needs of the people who are PDAM customers.

The gaps that occur in the Banggai Regency PDAM make the author interested in conducting further research to analyze the quality of service of the Banggai Regency PDAM. This research will use the *servqual* method. The *servqual* method is a method for measuring service quality with the level of perceptions and expectations of consumers in the services provided by service providers. Then it will be continued with the *Importance Performance Analysis* (IPA) method which will be used in measuring the level of importance and performance so that the company can find out the attributes that need to be improved and maintained in service based on the Cartesian diagram and will produce a basis for customer satisfaction. Furthermore, the *Fishbone Diagram* will be used to analyze the consequences by finding and describing the factors that cause the existing problems.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

The research conducted is classified as a type of quantitative research. Quantitative research method is a process of finding knowledge that uses data in the form of numbers as a tool to analyze information about what you want to know. (Djollong, 2019). Researchers aim to analyze the quality of public services at PDAM Banggai Regency. In measuring reality and expectations in public services, the *Servqual* scale is used which includes five dimensions of service quality, namely *Tangibles*, *Reliability*, *Responsiveness*, *Assurance* and *Empathy*. This research will be conducted at the Regional Drinking Water Company of Banggai Regency, Central Sulawesi Province. Respondents of this study were consumers of PDAM Kab. Banggai. The independent variable in this study is service quality, while the dependent variable in this study is customer satisfaction. The population determined in this study was the community of PDAM service users in Banggai Regency and the sample used was 100 samples.

In this study, the instrument used was a questionnaire. A questionnaire is a tool used in research that contains several questions used to obtain information from respondents in terms of their personal and things that respondents know (Arikunto, 2006). The questionnaire will be distributed to customers of PDAM Kab. Banggai. The questionnaire contains questions about the quality of PDAM services that must be answered by respondents in accordance with what happened during the research. The questionnaire in this study uses the Likert scale measurement method.

Data collection techniques in this study by taking samples from the population using a questionnaire. Data analysis conducted in this study is quantitative data analysis. Quantitative data analysis is carried out with several steps, namely validity and reliability tests. Analysis of service quality in this study using data derived from the results of the questionnaire will be processed using the *Service Quality* and *Importance Performance Analysis* methods.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Research Instrument Test

3.1.1 Validity test

An instrument can be measured for validity using the validity test. The validity test criteria are if $r\text{-count} > r\text{-table}$ (with a significance of 0.05) then the questions on the instrument are declared valid. Conversely, if $r\text{-count} < r\text{-table}$ (with a significance of 0.05) then the question items on the instrument are declared invalid. (Engkus, 2019). Calculation of the validity test in this study using SPSS (*Statistical Program for Social Science*). In the calculation of the validity test there is an *r-table* which is a table of numbers that is useful in the results of the validity test of a research instrument. The *r-table* is used to read and determine the value of the *r-table* with $df = n - 2 = 98$ significance 0.05 so that the *r-table* value = 0.1966 is obtained. (IPB University, 2023). In this study there are service quality variables consisting of 5 dimensions. The following are the results of the validity test of each dimension:

a. Tangible

Table 1. Tangible dimension validity test results

No	Statement	r Count Hope (A)	r Count Reality (AA)	r Table	Conclusion
1.	I think the location of administrative services is built in such a way that customers feel comfortable	0,898	0,801	0,1966	Valid
2.	Well- groomed employees	0,861	0,774	0,1966	Valid

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3.	Materials used to explain customer needs are clear and organized	0,860	0,808	0,1966	Valid
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Source: SPSS 23 Data Processing

Based on Table 2 shows that the 3 statement items of the *Tangible* dimension based on expectations are declared valid because the value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$, namely A.1 (0.898 > 0.196), A.2 (0.861 > 0.196) and A.3 (0.860 > 0.196). While based on reality, namely AA.1 (0.801 > 0.196), AA.2 (0.774 > 0.196) and AA.3 (0.808 > 0.196).

b. Reliability

Table 2. Results of the validity test of the Reliability dimension

No.	Statement	r Count Hope (B)	r Count Reality (BB)	r Table	Conclusion
1.	Service inserving customer complaints (murky water, non-flowing water, and leaking pipes) in accordance with the promises written in the establish regulations	0,931	0,854	0,1966	Valid
2.	Employees are able to solve problems (cloudy water, non-flowing water, leaking pipes) that customers complain about	0,962	0,808	0,1966	Valid
3.	Employees deliver services clearly at the time of initial PDAM installation	0,928	0,852	0,1966	Valid
4.	Employees communicate that services are delivered in the time promised	0,950	0,856	0,1966	Valid
5.	Ease of customers submitting online complaints to the PDAM	0,875	0,725	0,1966	Valid

Source: SPSS 23 Data Processing

Based on Table 3 shows that the 5 statement items of the *Responsiveness* dimension based on expectations are declared valid because the value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$, namely C.1 (0.888 > 0.196), C.2 (0.942 > 0.196), C.3 (0.937 > 0.196), C.4 (0.916 > 0.196), and C.5 (0.911 > 0.196). While based on reality, namely CC.1 (0.774 > 0.196), CC.2 (0.819 > 0.196), CC.3 (0.875 > 0.196), CC.4 (0.824 > 0.196) and CC.5 (0.824 > 0.196).

c. Responsiveness

Table 3. Responsiveness dimension validity test results

No.	Statement	r Count Hope (C)	r Count Reality (CC)	r Table	Conclusion
1.	Employees are quick to respond when answering complaints from customers through online media such as whatsapp	0,888	0,774	0,1966	Valid
2.	Officers contact customers when they are unable to fulfill the specified repair appointment	0,942	0,819	0,1966	Valid
3.	PDAM resolves customer complaints correctly and quickly	0,937	0,875	0,1966	Valid
4.	Employees are willing to help customer complaints based on procedures	0,916	0,824	0,1966	Valid
5.	Responsiveness of employees in providing services to customer requests	0,911	0,824	0,1966	Valid

Source: SPSS 23 Data Processing

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Based on Table 2 shows that the 5 statement items of the *Reliability* dimension based on expectations are declared valid because the value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$, namely B.1 (0.931>0.196), B.2 (0.962>0.196), B.3 (0.928>0.196), B.4 (0.950>0.196), and B.5 (0.875>0.196). While based on reality, namely BB.1(0.854>0.196), BB.2 (0.808>0.196), BB.3 (0.852>0.196), BB.4 (0.856>0.196) and BB.5 (0.725>0.196).

d. Assurance

Table 4. Assurance dimension validity test results

No.	Statement	r Count Hope (D)	r Count Reality (DD)	r Table	Conclusion
1.	Employees foster trust from customers in handling complaints (non-flowing water, cloudy water, leaking pipes)	0,915	0,720	0,1966	Valid
2.	The use of PDAM Kab. Banggai services is guaranteed to be safe when making payment transactions	0,953	0,703	0,1966	Valid
3.	Employees have good knowledge of the service so that they can answer customer questions	0,946	0,755	0,1966	Valid

Source: SPSS 23 Data Processing

Based on Table 4 shows that 3 statement items of the *Assurance* dimension based on expectations are declared valid because the value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$, namely D.1 (0.915>0.196), D.2 (0.953>0.196) and D.3 (0.946>0.196). Meanwhile, based on reality, namely DD.1 (0.720>0.196), DD.2 (0.703>0.196) and DD.3 (0.755>0.196).

e. Empathy

Table 5. Empathy dimension validity test results

No.	Statement	r Count Hope (E)	r Count Reality (EE)	r Table	Conclusion
1.	Employees give full attention regarding service to customers	0,954	0,876	0,1966	Valid
2.	Employees are very concerned about the interests of customers	0,958	0,870	0,1966	Valid
3.	Employees understand the special needs of customers in the payment process	0,967	0,853	0,1966	Valid
4.	Employees provide services in accordance with office hours so as to make customers comfortable	0,951	0,775	0,1966	Valid

Source: SPSS 23 Data Processing

Based on Table 5 shows that the 5 statement items of the *Responsiveness* dimension based on expectations are declared valid because the value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$, namely E.1 (0.954>0.196), E.2 (0.958>0.196), E.3 (0.967>0.196) and E.4 (0.951>0.196). While based on reality, namely EE.1 (0.876>0.196), EE.2 (0.870>0.196), EE.3 (0.853>0.196) and EE.4 (0.775>0.196).

3.1.2 Reliability Test

Reliability test is a measurement that shows that the extent to which the results of a measurement can be trusted. Reliability refers to the level of reliability of something. *Reliable* means trustworthy, so another word is reliable. (Situmorang & Purba, 2019). Reliability will be measured using the *Cronbach Alpha* Technique. The questionnaire is said to be reliable if *Alpha Cronbach* > 0.60 and cannot be declared reliable if it is equal to 60 or < 0.60 (Sunnyoto, 2013).

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a. Tangible

Table 6. Tangible dimension reliability test results

Dimensions	Cronbach's item Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha	Conclusion
Tangible Expectations(A)	0,6	0,939	Reliable
Tangible Reality(AA)	0,6	0,895	Reliable

Source: SPSS 23 Data Processing

The results of the reliability test on the *Tangible* Expectation (A) dimension have a *Cronbach's Alpha* value (0.939) and *Tangible* Reality (AA) has a *Cronbach's Alpha* value (0.895) declared reliable because it is greater than 0.6.

b. Reliability

Table 7. Reliability test results of the Reliability dimension

Dimensions	<i>Cronbach's item Alpha</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	Conclusion
Reliability Expectation (B)	0,6	0,975	<i>Reliable</i>
Reliability Reality (BB)	0,6	0,931	<i>Reliable</i>

Source: SPSS 23 Data Processing

The results of the reliability test on the *Reliability* Expectation (B) dimension have a *Cronbach's Alpha* value (0.975) and *Reliability* Reality (BB) has a *Cronbach's Alpha* value (0.931) declared reliable because it is greater than 0.6.

c. Responsiveness

Table 8. Responsiveness dimension reliability test results

Dimensions	<i>Cronbach's item Alpha</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	Conclusion
<i>Responsiveness</i> Expectations (C)	0,6	0,972	<i>Reliable</i>
<i>Responsiveness</i> Reality (CC)	0,6	0,933	<i>Reliable</i>

Source: SPSS 23 Data Processing

The results of the reliability test on the Expected *Responsiveness* dimension (C) have a *Cronbach's Alpha* value (0.972) and Reality *Responsiveness* (CC) has a *Cronbach's Alpha* value (0.933) declared reliable because it is greater than 0.6.

d. Assurance

Table 9. Assurance dimension reliability test results

Dimensions	<i>Cronbach's item Alpha</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	Conclusion
<i>Assurance</i> Expectation (D)	0,6	0,971	<i>Reliable</i>
<i>Assurance</i> Reality (DD)	0,6	0,853	<i>Reliable</i>

Source: SPSS 23 Data Processing

The results of the reliability test on the *Assurance* Expectation (D) dimension have a *Cronbach's Alpha* value (0.971) and *Assurance* Reality (DD) has a *Cronbach's Alpha* value (0.853) declared reliable because it is greater than 0.6.

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e. Empathy

Table 10. Empathy dimension reliability test results

Dimensions	Cronbach's item Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha	Conclusion
Empathy Expectation(E)	0,6	0,983	Reliable
Empathy Reality(EE)	0,6	0,933	Reliable

Source: SPSS 23 Data Processing

The results of the reliability test on the *Empathy* Expectation (E) dimension have a *Cronbach's Alpha* value (0.983) and *Empathy* Reality (EE) has a *Cronbach's Alpha* value (0.933) declared reliable because it is greater than 0.6.

3.2 Service Quality Analysis

Calculation of service quality using the *Servqual* method is done by looking at the performance level and the level of expectations. *Gap* value is the calculation of the reduction in the value of the perception of the service with the expected value desired by the customer. The *Service Quality* value is obtained from the calculation of each attribute using the formula. The following are the results of the calculation of the *Gap* value and Service Quality of each attribute:

Table 11. Service Quality of each dimension

No	Statement	Reality	Hope	GAP	Service Quality(Q)
<i>Tangible</i>					
1	I think the location of administrative services is built in such a way that customers feel comfortable (A1)	3,990	3,100	0,890	0,777
2	Employees are well-groomed (A2)	3,930	3,460	0,470	1,136
3	The material used to explain customer needs is clear and organized (A3)	3,860	3,100	0,760	1,245
<i>Reliability</i>					
1	Service in serving customer complaints (murky water, non-flowing water, and leaking pipes) in accordance with the promises written in the regulations that have been set (B1)	3,950	2,760	1,190	1,431
2	Employees are able to solve problems (cloudy water, non-flowing water, leaking pipes) that customers complain about (B2)	4,020	2,980	1,040	1,349
3	Employees convey services clearly at the beginning of PDAM installation (B3)	3,970	3,240	0,730	1,225
4	Employees convey that the service is in accordance with the promised time (B4)	3,990	2,980	1,010	1,339
5	Ease of customers submitting complaints online to the PDAM (B5)	2,670	3,870	- 1,200	0,690
<i>Responsiveness</i>					
1	Employees are quick to respond when answering complaints from customers through online media such as whatsapp (C1)	2,780	3,920	-1,140	0,709
2	Officers contact customers when unable to fulfill the specified repair appointment (C2)	2,750	3,890	-1,120	0,707
3	PDAM resolves customer complaints correctly and quickly (C3)	3,890	2,780	1,110	1,399
4	Employees are willing to help customer complaints based on procedures (C4)	3,840	3,010	0,830	1,276
5	Employee responsiveness in providing services to customer requests (C5)	3,860	3,010	0,850	1,282

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Assurance					
1	Employees foster trust from customers in handling complaints (non-flowing water, cloudy water, Leaking pipes) (D1)	3,820	2,890	0,930	1,322
2	The use of PDAM Kab. Banggai services is guaranteed to be safe when making payment transactions (D2)	3,380	3,940	- 0,560	0,858
3	Employees have good knowledge of the service so that they can answer customer questions (D3)	3,940	3,300	0,640	1,194
Empathy					
1	Employees give full attention regarding service to customers (E1)	3,900	3,140	0,760	1,242
2	Employees are very concerned about the interests of customers (E2)	3,880	3,100	0,780	1,252
3	Employees understand the special needs of customers in the payment process (E3)	3,840	3,060	0,780	1,255
4	Employees provide services in accordance with office hours so as to make customers comfortable (E4)	3,950	3,400	0,550	1,162

Source: SPSS 23 data processing

Based on Table 12 shows that there are several statement attributes that have negative *Gap* values such as attribute B5 worth (-1,200), attribute C1 worth (-1,140), C2 worth (-1,120) and D2 worth (-0,560). So it can be seen that the negative *Gap* value is still found in

4 *Servqual* dimensions, namely in the dimensions of *Tangible*, *Reliability*, *Responsiveness* and *Assurance*. Meanwhile, the dimension that does not have a negative *Gap* value is the *Empathy* dimension, which means that the performance of PDAM Kab. Banggai in the *Empathy* dimension has exceeded customer expectations. The lowest negative *gap* value is in the *Assurance* dimension at attribute D2 with a value of (-0.560) while the highest negative *gap* value is in the *Responsiveness* dimension at attribute C1 with a value of (-1.140). This shows that there is a mismatch between the priorities submitted by customers and the quality of service provided by the company.

In this case, the more negative the *gap* value obtained indicates that the company has the worst performance in the aspect of service quality. In table 12, it is known that there is each of the lowest to highest negative value gaps such as in the *Assurance* dimension at attribute D2, namely the use of PDAM Kab. Banggai services is guaranteed to be safe when making payment transactions with a *gap* of (-0.560). The resulting *gap* at attribute D2 is negative because one of the methods of paying bills by PDAM Kab. Banggai is still fairly insecure, namely officers still make billing from house to house with a note recording system after which it is reported back to the office to be recapitulated. This can be detrimental to customers because *double* payments can occur if payment has been made at the office but the officer is still collecting at home because the list of customers to be billed brought by the officer has not been updated so that *miss communication* can occur.

In the *Responsiveness* dimension attribute C2, namely the officer contacts the customer when he cannot fulfill the specified repair promise with a gap of (-1.120). The resulting *gap* at the C2 attribute is negative because there are reports of customer complaints such as the need for repairs to leaking pipes and have been received by the PDAM. In general, it is resolved properly and correctly but not carried out according to the promise. For example, customers receive information from officers that repairs will be carried out before the hour mentioned by the officer. But what happens in the field is that the repair time is not carried out as informed by the officer. This can cause *miss communication* between officers and customers if officers do not contact customers when they cannot fulfill the specified repair promise so that they can disappoint customers.

In the *Responsiveness* dimension at attribute C1, namely employees are responsive when answering complaints from customers through online media such as WhatsApp. The resulting *gap* at attribute C1 is negative because PDAM Kab. Banggai has not received customer complaints through online media because it still does not have an online media account such as *whatsapp* which *officially* belongs to PDAM Kab. Banggai. So that customers mostly make complaints by coming directly to the PDAM Kab. Banggai office. This causes employees to be less responsive to answering complaints from customers.

In the *Reliability* dimension at attribute B5, namely the ease with which customers can submit online complaints to the PDAM with a *gap* of (-1.200). The resulting *gap* at attribute C2 is negative because PDAM Kab. Banggai only receives customer complaints directly by coming to the PDAM Kab. Banggai office and still does not have a social media account. So it is less effective because it takes longer for customers to make complaints.

3.3 Importance Performance Analysis

Data analysis using the IPA model is carried out to determine the position of each attribute of each in the service of PDAM Kab. Banggai based on the level of perceptions and expectations of consumers. Cartesian diagrams will be made using SPSS *software* which will be divided into four regions bounded by the average value of the level of all attributes on the X-axis and Y-axis. Then it will be obtained in one quadrant there are attributes that most affect customer satisfaction. In the quadrant is an attribute that needs to be prioritized by the Company because the attribute is considered very important by consumers but the level of

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implementation is still not satisfactory. The following is a Cartesian diagram of the research results:

Figure 1. Cartesian diagram of the research results The following is a mapping of service attributes Based on the Cartesian diagram in Figure 1 which is divided into 4 quadrants:

a. Quadrant I

Quadrant I contains attributes that are very important to customers and have a major effect on customer satisfaction but in reality the PDAM Kab. Banggai still cannot fulfill customer desires. Therefore, quadrant I contains service attributes that have a very low level of customer satisfaction so that the attributes in quadrant I are the top priorities that are important to make improvements. Here are some attributes contained in quadrant I that need to be improved in order to increase customer satisfaction:

Attribute D2 the use of PDAM Kab. Banggai services is guaranteed to be safe when making payment transactions

Attribute C1 employees are quick to respond when answering complaints from customers through online media such as WhatsApp.

Attribute C2 staff contact the customer when unable to fulfill the specified repair appointment Attribute B5 ease of customers submitting complaints online to the PDAM

b. Quadrant II

Quadrant II contains attributes that need to be maintained in quality because based on customer satisfaction, PDAM Kab. Banggai has been satisfied with the services provided by the PDAM Kab. Banggai so that it must continue to maintain its quality so that customers can continue to feel satisfaction so as not to disappoint customers. The following are the attributes contained in quadrant II that need to be maintained:

A2 attribute employees are well-groomed

Attribute E4 employees provide services in accordance with office hours so as to make customers comfortable

Attribute D3 employees have good knowledge of the service so that they can answer customer questions

c. Quadrant III

Quadrant III contains attributes that are considered to have a low importance value for customers. However, the importance and satisfaction values of some of these attributes have equally low values so that they are a low priority for the Banggai District PDAM to make improvements. The existence of these attributes has no effect on the level of customer satisfaction because they are attributes whose performance is considered normal so that it would be a waste if improvements are made in the hope of increasing customer satisfaction but customers feel these attributes are not important. In quadrant III there are no research attributes that are in accordance with what is expected but are not a top priority for improvement.

d. Quadrant IV

Quadrant IV contains attributes that already meet customer satisfaction but have low expectation values for customers so that it is better for the PDAM Kab. Banggai focuses more on quadrant I as the top priority for improvement. The following attributes are contained in quadrant IV:

A1: The location of administrative services is built in such a way that customers feel comfortable

A3: Materials used to explain customer needs are clear and organized

B1: Service in serving customer complaints (murky water, non-flowing water, and leaking pipes) in accordance with the promises written in the regulations that have been set.

B2: Employees are able to solve problems (cloudy water, non-flowing water, leaking pipes) that customers complain about.

B3: Employees clearly communicate the service at the time of initial PDAM installation.

B4: Employees convey that the service is in accordance with the promised time

C3 :PDAM resolves customer complaints correctly and quickly.

C4 : Employees are willing to help customer complaints based on procedures

C5 : Responsiveness of employees in providing services to customer requests

D1 : Employees foster trust from customers in handling complaints (non-flowing water, cloudy water, leaking pipes)

E1 : Employees give full attention regarding services to customers

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E2 : Employees are very concerned about the interests of customers.

E3 :Employees understand the special needs of customers in the payment process.

3.4 Fishbone Diagram Analysis

Fishbone Diagram is a useful method to hypothesize the chain of causes and effects. The main function of the *fishbone* diagram is to analyze the consequences by finding and describing the factors that cause a problem. In an effort to determine factors that can be causes that have an influence on a problem. In this study, based on Figure 4.1 found in quadrant I are four attributes that are the top priority for improvement, namely attributes D2, C2, C1 and B5. Therefore, a *Fishbone diagram* is made to find out the causes and consequences of the problems that exist in this study to get solutions for improvement. The following *Fishbone diagram* of the four attributes that are the top priority for improving service quality:

a. D2 Attributes

The following is a *Fishbone Diagram* of the D2 attribute which is one of the top priorities for improvement in aspects of service quality:

Fishbone Diagram of D2 attribute

Based on Figure 4.2 there are several things that cause the low level of customer satisfaction attribute D2. Therefore, based on several factors that are the source of the cause of dissatisfaction, the proposed improvements given to the PDAM Kab. Banggai are as follows:

Table 13. Proposed improvements to the D2 attribute

Improvement Attributes	Factor	Causes	Proposed Improvements
Service users of PDAM Kab. Banggai are guaranteed to be safe when making payment transactions	Human	Officers are not thorough during the bill payment process	Double-checking before invoicing customers for payment
	Methods	Manual payments system (through counters and house-to-house billing)	Cooperate with third parties such as banks and Outlets (indomaret, alfamidi, etc.)
	Machine	Payment recording tool with manual writing	Create a payment application that is directly connected to the PDAM account so that there is no manipulation during the payment process.

b. C2 Attributes

The following is a *Fishbone Diagram* of the C2 attribute which is one of the top priorities for improvement in aspects of service quality:

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Fishbone Diagram of C2 attribute

Based on Figure 3, it is found that the things that cause customers to feel less satisfied with the services provided by PDAM Kab. Banggai, namely contained in the C2 attribute so that several factors cause customers to feel less satisfied. Proposed improvements that can be given to the PDAM Kab. Banggai are as follows:

Table 14. Proposed improvements to the C2 attribute

Improvement Attributes	Factor	Causes	Proposed Improvements
	Human	Lack of responsibility from PDAM officials to convey and provide understanding that they cannot fulfill the specified repair promise.	Instill a sense of responsibility in staff and openness to Customers to contact customers as soon as possible if something happens or cannot fulfill the repair promise as specified.
Employees are quick to respond when answering complaints from customers through online media	Methods	There is no provision for contacting the customer if they are unable to fulfill the repair appointment.	The need to create an SOP so that it has standard provisions for contacting customers if they cannot fulfill repair promises
	Machine	Inadequate means of contacting customers	Provide a means to contact customers

c. C1 Attributes

The following is a *Fishbone Diagram* of the C1 attribute which is one of the top priorities for improvement in aspects of service quality:

Figure 4. Fishbone Diagram of C1 attribute Based on Figure 4, there are several things that cause the low level of customer satisfaction attribute C1. Therefore, based on several factors that are the source of the cause of dissatisfaction, the proposed improvements given to the PDAM Kab. Banggai are as follows:

Table 15. Proposed improvements to the C1 attribute

Improvement Attributes	Factor	Causes	Proposed Improvements
	Human	There is no 24-hour active <i>Customer Service</i> to receive customer complaints	Recruiting <i>Customer Service</i> and implementing a 24-hour work shift system to be available if there are complaints via message or call.
Employees are quick to respond when answering complaints from customers through online media such as <i>whatsapp</i>	Methods	The online complaint service system has not been well planned	Implement a 24-hour online complaint service to respond quickly to customer complaints.
	Machine	Does not yet have online media such as <i>whatsapp</i>	Provide social media accounts that are always updated to provide information about the PDAM and are responsive when there are complaints from customers online.

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d. Attribute B5

The following is a *Fishbone Diagram* of attribute B5 which is one of the top priorities for improvement in aspects of service quality:

Figure 5. Fishbone Diagram of attribute B5

Based on Figure 5, it is found that the things that cause customers to feel less satisfied with the services provided by PDAM Kab. Banggai, namely contained in the C2 attribute so that several factors cause customers to feel less satisfied. Proposed improvements that can be given to the PDAM Kab. Banggai are as follows:

Table 16. Proposed improvements for attribute B5

Improvement Attributes	Factor	Causes	Proposed Improvements
	Human	There is no officer available when there is an online complaint	Implement a workshift system for officers who are available when there is a complaint via message or call.
Ease of customers submitting complaints online to the PDAM Kab. Banggai	Methods	Complaint services are only carried out directly at the PDAM office in Banggai Kab.	Implement online grievance services through social media
	Machine	The PDAM does not yet provide a medium to submit complaints online	Provide media for customers to submit complaints online such as providing a PDAM contact number that is always active 24 hours.

3.5 Proposed improvements given to the PDAM

3.6

Table 17. Proposed improvements and PDAM's response to the proposed improvements

Proposed Improvements	Explanation from PDAM Kab. Banggai
Double-checking before invoicing customers for payment	The PDAM accepts the proposed improvements to conduct a re-inspection before billing payments to customers
Cooperate with third parties such as banks and outlets (indomaret, alfamidi, etc.)	The PDAM has cooperated with third parties, namely the Post Office. However, it has not yet cooperated with banks and outlets (indomaret, alfamidi, etc.). The PDAM accepted the proposed improvements so that it can further cooperate with banks and outlets (indomaret, alfamidi, etc.).
Create a payment application that is directly connected to the PDAM account so that there is no manipulation during the payment process.	The PDAM in the process of implementing payments through counters by using a system on a computer that can be connected directly to the PDAM account so that there is no data manipulation during the payment process.
Instill a sense of responsibility in staff and openness to customers to contact customers as soon as possible if something happens or cannot fulfill the repair	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The PDAM still continues to instill a sense of responsibility in staff and openness to customers to contact customers as soon as possible if something

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promise as specified.	<p>happens or cannot fulfill the repair promise as specified.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The PDAM accepts the proposed improvements so that it can be planned to reward officers who behave as service officers should, such as having a sense of responsibility.
The need to create an SOP so that it has standard provisions for contacting customers if they cannot fulfill repair promises	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The PDAM explained that it always contacts customers when it cannot fulfill repair promises. However, it is not a standard provision so that it becomes an obligation. So there may still be officers who are negligent by not contacting customers if they cannot fulfill repair promises. Furthermore, it will be used as a standard provision for officers to contact customers if they cannot fulfill the repair promise.
Provide a means to contact customers	The PDAM accepts the proposed improvements and will provide a means to contact customers in the future.
Recruiting <i>Customer Service</i> and implementing a 24-hour work shift system to be available if there are complaints via message or call. Implement a 24-hour online complaint service to respond quickly to customer complaints.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The PDAM is still in the process of trying to create a <i>whatsapp</i> media account that can be active 24 hours can be contacted via chat. However, it can only answer questions about payment bills. So that it has not been done to answer or receive complaints from customers The PDAM accepts the proposed improvements to further receive complaints through <i>whatsapp</i> media as previously done to answer questions about payment bills.
Implement a work shift system for officers who are available when there is a complaint via message or call.	Currently, the PDAM only receives complaints directly through the office. However, the PDAM received a proposal for improvement so that in the future it will provide officers with a work shift system who are available when there are complaints via message or <u>call</u> .
Implement online grievance services through social media	<p>The PDAM is still in the process of trying to create a <i>whatsapp</i> media account that can be active 24 hours can be contacted via chat. However, it can only answer questions about payment bills. So that it has not been done to answer or receive complaints from customers</p> <p>The PDAM accepts the proposed improvements to further receive complaints through <i>whatsapp</i> media as previously done to answer questions about payment bills.</p>
Provide media for customers to submit complaints online such as providing a PDAM contact number that is always active 24 hours.	The PDAM accepts the proposed improvements to further receive complaints through <i>whatsapp</i> media for 24 hours as previously done to answer customer questions regarding payment bills. Furthermore, complaints that have been submitted will be processed during working hours.

4. CONCLUSION

The results of the *Service Quality* analysis of the service quality of PDAM Kab. Banggai obtained a negative *Gap* value found in the *Reliability* dimension at attribute B5 of (-1,200), namely the ease with which customers can submit complaints online to the PDAM, in the *Responsiveness* dimension obtained a negative *Gap* value at attribute C1 of (-1,140), namely employees are responsive when answering complaints from customers through online media such as *whatsapp* and at attribute C2 with a negative *Gap* of (-1,120), namely the officer contacts the customer when he cannot fulfill the specified repair promise, then in the *Assurance* dimension with a negative *Gap* of (-0.560). The lowest *Gap* value is in the *Reliability* dimension at attribute B5, which is equal to (-1,200).

The results of the analysis using *Importance Performance Analysis* obtained 4 attributes that are among the top priorities for improvement, namely the attributes contained in quadrant I. The four attributes that are the top

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priorities for improvement are the ease with which customers can submit complaints online to the PDAM, employees are responsive when answering complaints from customers through online media such as *whatsapp*, officers contact customers when they cannot fulfill the specified repair promise and the use of PDAM services Kab. Banggai is guaranteed to be safe when making payment transactions.

The proposed improvements given to PDAM Kab. Banggai are as follows: Attribute D2 conducting a re-check before billing payments to customers, collaborating with third parties such as banks and outlets (indomaret, alfamidi, etc.) and making payment applications directly linked to PDAM accounts so that there is no manipulation during the payment process. Attribute C2 instill a sense of responsibility in officers and openness to customers to contact customers as soon as possible if something happens or cannot fulfill the specified repair promise, the need to make SOPs so that they have standard provisions for contacting customers if they cannot fulfill repair promises and provide facilities to contact customers. Attribute C1: recruit Customer Service and enforce a 24-hour work shift system so that they are available if there are complaints via messages or calls, enforce online complaint services for 24 hours so that they are quick to respond to customer complaints and provide social media accounts that are always updated to provide information about the PDAM and are responsive when there are complaints from customers online. Attribute B5: impose a work shift system for officers who are available when there are complaints via messages or calls, enforce online complaint services through social media and provide media for customers to submit complaints online such as providing PDAM contact numbers that are always active 24 hours.

The proposed improvements have been given to the PDAM and have been well received by the PDAM of Banggai Regency. There are proposed improvements that are still in the trial process for implementation and are still not fully improved because they are still being carried out in stages. However, other proposed improvements were well received by the PDAM for further follow-up by the PDAM Kab. Banggai to improve service quality.

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